

Susa mint: 311-301 BC

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This paper is the final component in a trilogy¹ that documents a die study of the large denomination coinage issued from the Susa mint prior to 300 BC. It examines the Alexandrine coinage of Seleukos struck in the period 311/0-304/3BC,² prior to the introduction of coinage bearing his own name. Three groups (Groups 5-7) are recognized in this coinage. Groups 5 and 6, bear a laurel wreath symbol, which in the case of Group 6 is accompanied by a range of other symbols. These two groups were struck simultaneously during the Babylonian War in the period c. 311/0-309/8 BC. Group 7 post-dates the Babylonian War. It is characterised by the presence of the anchor symbol, which displaced the laurel wreath as the primary symbol on the coinage. On the last reverse dies of Group 7 this anchor symbol was erased, a phenomenon previously identified on coinage from the mints of Babylon II and Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis), dated to c. 305/4-304/3 BC.³ This was a synchronous event across Seleukos's mints operating in Babylonia and Susiana, one that provides a firm chronological peg for the last of the Susa issues (Group 7) in the name of Alexander, an updating of a decade relative to that proposed in *Seleucid Coins*.⁴

HISTORY OF SCHOLARSHIP

Newell's study of the Eastern Seleucid Mints (*ESM*) included the first coherent examination of the earliest Seleukid coinage of Susa, issued in the name of Alexander.⁵ For sixty years it remained the primary reference on the subject. It was the basis of Price's 1991 typology of the sequence of Susa Alexanders issued under Seleukos.⁶ Subsequently, Kritt (*ESMS*)⁷ undertook a die analysis of this coinage, the conclusions of which Houghton and Lorber adopted in *Seleucid Coins Part 1 (SC)*.⁸ Recently, Price's wreath group coinage (Susa Group 5; Price 3853-60), previously attributed to the satrap Aspeisas (317/6 -312/1 BC), was conclusively downdated to the period c. 311/0-309/8 BC,⁹ a contemporary of the earliest Susa issues of Seleukos I, struck in the name of Alexander (Price 3861-3874).

The downdating of the wreath group challenges the current understanding¹⁰ of the extent and chronology of the Seleukid issues that were struck in the name of Alexander. The following catalogue and die study extends the Susa Group 5 tetradrachm analysis to the entirety of the large denomination Alexandrine coinage (gold staters and silver tetradrachms) struck at Susa under Seleukos I, with the objective of establishing a new understanding and revised chronology.

¹ Taylor (2019a) for Susa Groups 1-4; Taylor (2019b) for Susa Group 5.

² Dates are referenced to the Macedonian lunar calendar year commencing September/October each year.

³ Taylor (2015).

⁴ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 67-71.

⁵ Newell (1938): 107-112. Newell's Series I, Groups A-D which he dated to c. 310-300 BC.

⁶ Price (1991): 484-489.

⁷ Kritt (1997): 5-7, pls. 1-5.

⁸ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 67-71.

⁹ Taylor (2019b).

¹⁰ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 67-71.

CATALOGUE

The previously published catalogue of Group 5 tetradrachms is not repeated here, although the interpretation that follows takes full account of and refers to the Group 5 study.¹¹ The catalogue commences with the gold stater of Groups 5-7, followed by the tetradrachms of Groups 6-7. The latter continues the die numbering established for Group 5, so that the first tetradrachm entry commences with die pair A9-P46. The coins were struck from unadjusted dies. The weight recorded against each specimen is in grams. An asterisk adjacent to a catalogue entry denotes a coin illustrated on the accompanying plates (Plates 1-3).

AV Staters

Group 5

c. 311/0-309/8 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with coiled serpent.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, AI to l. below wing, Π to r. below wing.

5.8 AI, Π

Price 3856A; SC -; ESM -.

	<i>Obv.</i>	<i>Rev.</i>	<i>gms.</i>	<i>Provenance</i>
1. *	Av1	Pav1	8.32	New York, ANS 1944.100.35520; Price 3856A.

Group 6

c. 311/0-309/8 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with sphinx.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, AY to l. below wing and Bee to r. below wing.

6.3 AY, Bee

Price 3688 corr. (AY not LY) ; SC 161; ESM -.

2.	Av2	Pav2	8.55	Numismatik Lanz München 102 (28 May 2001), lot 196; Bank Leu 38 (13 May 1986), lot 70.
3. *	Av2	Pav2	8.55	London, BM 1878,0301.72; GC30.3688(a).
4.	Av2	Pav2	8.54	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 56 (9 May 2019), lot 232.
5.	Av2	Pav3	8.53	Leu Numismatik Web Auction 4 (24 Jun. 2018), lot 147.
6.	Av2	Pav4	8.55	Fritz Rudolf Künker 295 (25 Sep. 2017), lot 253.
7. *	Av2	Pav5	8.54	New York, ANS 1944.100.35526. Pav5 – crossbar of the A in the AY mint control very lightly engraved, almost imperceptible, so that the mint control appears as LY to the naked eye.

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with gryphon.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below, ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, EB above Horsehead l. above TI in l. field.

¹¹ Taylor (2019b).

6.7 **EB / Horned Horsehead l./ TI** Price 3864; SC 160; ESM 285.

8. * Av3 Pav6 8.57 London, BM 1922,1115.12; GC30.3864; Price 3864; ESM 285.

Group 7

c. 305/4-304/3 BC

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with sphinx.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, **Α** to l. below wing, AP to r. below wing.

7.5 **Α, AP** Price -; SC -; ESM -.

The **Α** mint control is an engraving variant of the **Α** mint control on the type 7.2-7.4 tetradrachms.

9. * Av4 Pav7 8.56 Numismatica Ars Classica 84 (20 May 2015), lot 688.

Plated counterfeits

Obverse: Head of Athena r. wearing crested Corinthian helmet adorned with sphinx.

Reverse: ΙΑΣΙΑΕ to l., ΑΛΕΞΑΝΑΡ to r., Nike standing l. holding wreath and stylis, AY below l. wing and Bee below r. wing.

Copying type 6.3 AY, Bee Imitating Price 3688; SC 161.

10.	a1	p1	5.11	New York, ANS 1944.100.26658.
11. *	a1	p2	4.45	London, BM G. 1299; GC30.3688d.
12. *	a2	p2	4.28	London, BM G. 1298; GC30.3688c.
13.	a2	p2	3.15	London, BM 1978,1001.2; GC30.3688b.
14.	a2	p2	4.08	New York, ANS 1944.100.26660.
15.	a2	p3	4.44	New York, ANS 1944.100.26657.
16.	a2	p3	4.28	New York, ANS 1944.100.26659.

AR Tetradrachms

Obverse: Head of beardless Herakles r. wearing lion skin headdress; dotted border.

Reverse: ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ below (exception 6.1), ΑΛΕΞΑΝΔΡΟΥ to r., Zeus *Aëtrophoros* seated l. on a high-backed throne, symbols and/or mint marks in l. field, Greek monogram and letter mint controls beneath throne; dotted border.

Zeus is depicted with legs side by side (parallel legs) on all but types 5.5-5.7, 6.1, 6.5, some of 6.6 and 6.8 where the portrayal is that of Zeus's right leg drawn back behind his left leg in a crossing legs depiction. Both depictions of Zeus's legs are to be found on the coins of type 6.6.

Group 5

c. 311/0-309/8 BC

Refer Taylor (2019b) for catalogue of Group 5 tetradrachms.

Struck from eight obverse dies and 45 reverse dies in a catalogue of 103 tetradrachms

Group 6

c. 311/0-309/8 BC

Die numbering follows sequentially from Group 5.

6.1	Amphora, ΛY		Price 3690A (Babylon), SC -; ESM -.	
	Zeus depicted with crossed legs.			
17. *	A9	P46	16.80	New York, ANS 1944.100.35527. ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ is absent from the legend.
6.2	Bee, ΛY		Price 3689 (Babylon); SC 164.5 corr.; ESM -.	
	The ΛY mint mark is an engraving variant of AY. SC mistakenly identified ΛY as AY on Cat. Nos. 18 and 20.			
18. *	A10	P47	17.03	London, BM 2002,0101.957; Hersh Coll.; Price 3689.
19.	A10	P48	17.10	Numismatik Naumann 10 (1 Dec. 2013), lot 108.
20.	A10	P48?	16.96	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2475.
6.4	Bee, AY		Price 3689 var. (Babylon); SC 164.5; ESM -.	
21. *	A10	P49	17.07	Savoca Coins 2nd Blue Auction (3-4 May 2019), lot 523. A10 die wear indicates that this coin was struck after Cat. No. 18 but prior to Cat. No. 19. Thus the ΛY and AY mint controls were struck in an interwoven manner suggesting that the letter Λ was no more than an engraving variant of the letter A.
22.	A11	P50	17.05	Ars Coin Wein SKU:G170; Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 345.
23.	A11	P50	17.17	Roma Numismatics E-Live 3 (25 Oct. 2018), lot 341.
24.	A11	P50	16.58	CNG 49 (17 Mar. 1999), lot 225.
25. *	A11	P51	17.14	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 280.
26.	A11	P51	17.10	NBJ The Art of Numismatics sku-g96 (2019).
27.	A11	P51	16.98	CNG eAuction 325 (23 Apr. 2014), lot 261.
28.	A11	P52	17.10	CNG eAuction 423 (27 Jun. 2018), lot 193.
29.	A11	P53	17.09	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 9 (28 Jun. 2014), lot 242.
30.	A11	P53	16.26	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18250467.
31.	A11	P54	16.91	CNG eAuction 397 (17 May 2017), lot 203.
32.	A11	P54	17.10	CNG eAuction 399 (14 Jun. 2017), lot 227.
33.	A11	P55	17.13	Gorny & Mosch Giessener Münzhandlung 257 (15 Oct. 2018), lot 307.
34. *	A11	P56	17.14	Heritage 3073 (25-29 Apr. 2019), lot 32019; Roma Numismatics XVI (20 Sep. 2018), lot 381.
35.	A11	P56	16.84	New York, ANS 1944.100.35560; Price 3689 (ANS). AY was misread as ΛY by Price on this coin.
36.	A11	P57	17.18	Pars Coins PCW-G6374 (2019).
37. *	A11	P57	17.12	Roma Numismatics XVII (28 Mar. 2019), lot 561; Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (28 Jun. 2018), lot 353.
38.	A11	P57?	16.81	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2473.
39.	A11	P57?	16.95	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2474.
40.	A12	P58	16.02	ESMS Al.16, pl. 3, 16; Failaka Hoard (1984) CH 8.256, 23.

6.5 Wreath, Shield / Horsehead, **BE** Price 3865; SC 164.4b; ESM 286.
Zeus depicted with crossed legs throughout type 6.5.

41. *	A11 recut	P59	15.93	CNG eAuction 397 (17 May 2017), lot 202; Ponterio 130 (30 Apr. 2004), lot 1329. A11 recut – die retouched and refaced to remove flow lines, reducing detail on the outermost trailing mane of lionskin headdress.
42.	A11 recut	P59 ?	16.85	ESMS Al.12, pl.2, 12; SNG Sweden (Von Post), 556.
43. *	A11 recut	P60	16.88	London, BM 2002,0101.950; Hersh Coll.
44. *	A11 recut2	P60	16.96	LWHT Coll. 208; Eukratides Ancient Numismatics sku-br42; ex-W. K. Raymond Coll. A11 recut2 – die further recut on the neckline of lion skin headdress to remove die break.
45.	A11 recut2	P60	16.73	Noble Numismatics 91 (21-23 Jul. 2009), lot 3429; Noble 90 (31 Mar.-2 Apr. 2009), lot 3251.
46.	A11 recut2	P61	16.10	London Coin Galleries online auction 3 (10 Nov. 2016), lot 222.
47.	A11 recut2	P62	16.75	London, BM 1850,0412.5; GC 30.3865; Price 3865; ESM 286 α , pl. XXII, 4.
48. *	A12	P63	16.95	New York, ANS 1944.100.72213; ESM 286 β , pl. XXII, 5.
49.	A12	P64	16.98	CNG eAuction 381 (24 Aug. 2016), lot 224.
50.	A13	P65	16.93	Burtonsville, Md., B. Kritt Coll.; ESMS Al.10; pl.2, 10.
51. *	A13	P65	16.49	CNG eAuction 417 (28 Mar. 2018), lot 280; Spink (Dec. 1997).
52.	A14	P66	17.01	CNG eAuction 261 (3 Aug. 2011), lot 138; CNG 72 (14 Jun. 2006), lot 917; 'Seleucus I' Hoard, 2005 CH 10.265, 1634.
53. *	A14	P66	16.54	Emporium Hamburg 81 (23 Oct. 2018), lot 156.
54. *	A15	P67	16.83	Heritage 231912 (21 Mar. 2019), lot 63007.

6.6 Wreath, Shield / Horsehead, **BE / TI** Price 3866; SC 164.4a; ESM 287.
Zeus depicted variably in type 6.6, with either parallel legs, or crossed legs.

55.	A11 recut	P68	17.06	ESMS Al.9, pl.2, 9; Schulten (27-29 Mar. 1990), lot 408. Zeus with crossed legs.
56. *	A16	P69	16.85	London, BM 1936,0512.1; GC30.3866, Price 3866. Zeus with parallel legs.
57.	A16	P70	17.04	CNG eAuction 399 (14 Jun. 2017), lot 226. Zeus with crossed legs.
58.	A16	P70	16.80	ESMS Al.8, pl. 2, 8; Houghton (1983): CSE 1021; Leu 45 (26 May 1988), lot 253; Sotheby (30 Apr. 1958), lot 123.
59.	A16	P71	16.95	Gemini LLC XI (12 Jan. 2014), lot 596.1; ex-Richard Miller Coll.; CNG 60 (22 May 2002), lot 884. Zeus with parallel legs.

6.8 Wreath / Horsehead, **Δ I / Γ** Price 3863; SC 164.3; ESM 284.
Zeus depicted with crossed legs throughout type 6.8.

60.	A17	P72	16.82	Heritage 231902 (10 Jan. 2019), lot 62013.
61. *	A17	P72	17.12	CNG 100 (7 Oct. 2015), lot 1561.
62.	A17	P72	16.99	CNG eAuction 421 (30 May 2018), lot 235; Aureo & Calico 301 (13 Dec. 2017), lot 1018.
63.	A17	P72	17.00	Münzen & Medaillen 32 (20 Oct. 1966), lot 140; NFA Winter MBS (18 Dec. 1987), lot 108; Qazvin Hoard (IGCH 1796), Spaer (1975): Qazvin Hoard, CH 1.58, 19, fig. 12, 19.

SUSA MINT: 311-301 BC

64.	A17	P72	16.90	CNG 78 (14 May 2008), lot 901.
65.	A17	P73	16.88	Studio Numismatico Raffaele Negrini E-Live (16-17 May 2019), lot 110.
66.*	A17	P73	17.09	CNG 108 (16 May 2018), lot 281; Roma Numismatics IV (30 Sep. 2012), lot 421.
67.	A17	P74	17.14	Goldberg 90 (2 Feb. 2016), lot 3096; Numismatica Ars Classica 88 (8 Oct. 2015), lot 578.
68.	A17	P74	16.86	Helios Numismatik 2 (25 Nov. 2008), lot 101.
69.	A17	P75	16.96	London, BM 2002,0101.949; Hersh Coll.; Price 3863.
70.	A17	P76	16.74	London, BM 1845,1217.145; GC30.3863; Price 3863; <i>ESM</i> 284, pl. XXII,2.
71.	A17	P76	17.01	CNG eAuction 265 (5 Oct. 2011) lot 170; CNG 76 (12 Sep. 2007), lot 773.
72.	A17	P76?	16.96	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2480.
73.	A18	P77?	13.89	<i>ESMS</i> Al.6, pl.1, 6; Pasargadae II Hoard, 14.
6.9	Wreath / Anchor / Bull's Head, ΔI/ I			Price 3862; <i>SC</i> 164.2; <i>ESM</i> 283.
74.*	A19	P78	16.85	London, BM 1847,0619.20; <i>ESM</i> 283, pl. XXII, 1.
6.10	Wreath / Anchor, Μ/ I			Price -, <i>SC</i> -; <i>ESM</i> -.
75.*	A19	P79	16.92	Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 337.
6.11	Wreath / Anchor, Μ/ Π			Price 3861 corr. (Π not Π); <i>SC</i> 164.1 (corr. Μ not Μ); <i>ESM</i> -.
76.*	A19	P80	17.03	Heritage 3037 (4 Jan. 2015), lot 29964.
77.	A19	P80	17.30	Hess-Leu 31 (6-7 Dec. 1966), lot 506; Qazvin Hoard (<i>IGCH</i> 1796), Spaer (1975): Qazvin Hoard, <i>CH</i> 1.58, 18, fig.12, 18.
Group 7				
c. 305/4-304/3 BC				
7.1	Anchor, AE			Price 3872; <i>SC</i> 164.6; <i>ESM</i> 290.
78.	A20	P81	16.55	<i>ESMS</i> Al.19, pl. 4, 19; Failaka Hoard (1984) <i>CH</i> 8.256, 24.
79.*	A20	P82	16.46	New York, ANS 1944.100.72224; <i>ESM</i> 290, pl. XXII, 9.
7.2	Anchor / Α , Σ / AP			Price -; <i>SC</i> 164.8c -; <i>ESM</i> -.
The Α mint control (also rendered Α on some dies) is usually weakly struck, or off-flan on some examples. On Cat. Nos. 83-84 it was omitted from two reverse dies, only to be added for subsequent striking from one of the dies (Cat. No. 85).				
79.	A21	P83	17.01	CNG eAuction 402 (26 Jul. 2017), lot 281. Left field monogram not visible on worn coin.
81.*	A21	P83	17.14	Pars Coins PCW-G6373 (2018).
82.	A21	P83	17.11	Heritage NYINC Sale 3072 (15-16 Jan. 2019), lot 35054 (HID02901242017); Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (28 Jun. 2018), lot 355.
7.3	Anchor/ -, Σ / AP			Price 3874; <i>SC</i> 164.8c; <i>ESM</i> 293.
This type was defined by Newell, Price, and Houghton and Lorber on the basis of the following two specimens which omitted the Α mint control from the reverse die. It was subsequently added to the P85 die (Cat. No. 85).				
83.	A21	P84	17.09	<i>ESM</i> 293, pl. XXII, 13.
84.*	A21	P85	16.48	London, BM 2002,0101.956; Hersh Coll.

7.2	Anchor / Σ / AP			Price -; SC -; ESM -.
85. *	A21	P85	17.12	Roma Numismatics E-Live 2 (30 Aug. 2018), lot 346. P85 recut – engraved on worn die below anchor symbol.
86.	A21	P86	17.05	CNG eAuction 421 (30 May 2018), lot 239; Freeman & Sear (18 Jan. 2002).
87.	A21	P86?	16.95	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2478.
88.	A21	P86?	17.05	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2479.
89. *	A21	P87	17.07	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 281.
90. *	A22	P88	17.07	Gorny & Mosch 265 (14 Oct. 2019), lot 229.
7.4	Anchor / Σ / Δ P			Price -; SC -; ESM -.
	On this type the AP mint control beneath the throne of Zeus has been rendered as Δ P in the engraving of the die.			
91. *	A21 recut	P89	17.17	CNG eAuction 300 (10 Apr. 2013), lot 73. A21 recut – neckline of lionskin headdress recut. Advanced die break on cheek. Rev. left field monogram struck on flan edge so that only partially visible.
7.6	Anchor, Kantharos /			Price -; SC 164.7; ESM -.
	Θ E rendered in ligate monogram form on reverse dies P91 and P94.			
92.	A23	P90	17.16	Pars Coins II (VCoins 340) (15 Jul. 2019), lot 133.
93.	A23	P91	17.08	Pars Coins PCW-G6594; Heritage 3067 (6 Sep. 2018), lot 33200. P91 – Θ E rendered in ligate monogram form .
94.	A23	P91	17.08	Heritage 3076 (9 Sep. 2019), lot 33011.
95.	A23	P91	17.03	Heritage 231912 (21 Mar. 2019), lot 63039.
96.	A23	P92	16.98	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2476
97.	A23	P92	16.89	Davesne, and Le Rider (1989): Meydancikkale Hoard 2477.
98.	A23	P93	17.17	Triskeles Auction 334 (7 Dec. 2018), lot 205; Stephen Album Rare Coins 31 (17 May 2018), lot17.
99.*	A23	P93	17.13	Roma Numismatics E-Sale 47 (28 Jun. 2018), lot 354.
100.	A23	P93	17.12	Heritage 231917 (25 Apr. 2019), lot 64009; Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 382.
101.	A23	P94	16.21	CNG eAuction 421 (30 May 2018), lot 237. P94 – Θ E rendered in ligate monogram form .
102.	A23	P94	17.10	CNG eAuction 421 (20 May 2018), lot 238; Aureo & Calicó 297 (18 Oct. 2017), lot 1007; Heritage 231607 (18 Feb. 2016), lot 63004. Due to an off-centre strike, only the right side of the anchor symbol is lightly struck on the flan edge.
7.7	Anchor Σ / AP			Price -; SC 164.8b; ESM -.
103. *	A23	P95	17.01	CNG webshop inventory no. 515847 (2019).
104. *	A23	P95	17.12	Pars Coins PCW-G6372 (2019).
105.	A23	P95	17.02	London, BM 2002,0101.955; ESMS Al.27, pl. 5, 27; Hersh (1998): no. 83, pl. 30, 83.
7.8	(Anchor erased) Σ / AP			Price -; SC -; ESM -.
106. *	A23	P95 recut1	17.18	LWHT Coll. 309; Pars Coins PCW-G6328 (2019). P95 recut – anchor incompletely erased from die, a vestige outline remains visible on the coin strike.
107. *	A23	P95 recut2	17.09	Roma Numismatics E-Live 1 (25 Jul. 2018), lot 282. P95 recut – further recut so that the anchor symbol is completely erased from die, leaving no vestige form on the coin strike.

7.9 Anchor/, Σ / ΔP Price 3873 var.; SC 164.8a var.; ESM 292 var.
 ΔP not AP. The ΔP mint mark was incorrectly read as AP by Price, SC, and ESM on the following coins from the BM, ANS and Berlin collections.

108. *	A24	P96	17.16	Pars Coins PCW-G6422 (2019).
109.	A24	P96	16.93	Pars Coins II/VAuctions 340 (15 Jul. 2019), lot 134.
110.	A24	P96	17.07	Stephen Album 31 (17-19 May 2018), lot 15.
111.	A24	P96	17.06	Heritage 231833 (16 Aug. 2018), lot 63007.
112. *	A24	P97	17.07	New York, ANS 1950.65.1.
113.	A24	P97	16.84	London, BM 2002,0101.954; Hersh Coll.
114.	A24	P98	17.04	London, BM 1921,0109.4; GC30.3873, Price 3873; ESM 292 γ, pl. XXII, 12.
115.	A24	P98	16.66	Berlin, Münzkabinett 18253838; ESM 292 β.
116. *	A24	P98	17.11	Gorny & Mosch 257 (15 Oct. 2018), lot 308.

7.10 Anchor/, Σ / AP Price 3873; SC 164.8a.; ESM 292.

117.	A24	P99	17.16	Pars Coins PCW-G6657 (2019).
118. *	A24	P100	17.04	NBJ Art of Numismatics sku-g18 (2019).
119.	A24	P100	17.09	NBJ Art of Numismatics sku-g91 (2019).
120.	A24	P100	n.r.	Hafnia Coins (Denmark) AG1020 (2019).
	A24	P100	17.11	Heritage 231840 (4 Oct. 2018), lot 61003.

7.11 (Anchor and monogram erased), Σ / AP Price -; SC -; ESM -.

121. *	A24	P100 recut	17.07	LWHT Coll. 311; Heritage 231917 (25 Apr. 2019), lot 64013; Roma Numismatics XVI (26 Sep. 2018), lot 383. P100 recut – anchor and left field monogram erased from die.
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COMMENTARY

Table 1 summarizes the sequence of issues established in the die study. It includes a concordance of the catalogue types with those of earlier primary references (SC, Price and ESM).¹² Each of Groups 5-7 is defined on the basis of a progression of mint marks accompanied by one or more symbols. Four issues of gold staters are identified; one in each of Groups 5 and 7, and two in Group 6. One of these gold staters, Type 7.5, is previously unrecorded. Twenty-six tetradrachm issues are identified in Groups 5-7, including four newly identified types, plus a number of variants and corrections to previously identified issues. These are tightly die linked in each group (Tables 1 and 2), indicative of compact, short duration emissions. No die links are identified between the groups but there is a clear progression in symbols and controls in the overall sequence of the three groups. The earliest types are defined by a single symbol, the laurel wreath on Group 5, and the amphora followed by the bee on the earliest of Group 6. The latter symbols are displaced by a laurel wreath, accompanied by one or more other symbols on Group 6, after which the wreath is discarded and the Seleukid anchor appears as the primary symbol on the tetradrachms of Group 7.

The silver coinage of Group 5¹³ bears a laurel wreath in the left field, unaccompanied by any other symbol. Beneath Zeus's throne a primary mint control persists throughout the group, accompanied by a progression of Greek letter secondary mint controls placed above the primary control. The sole

¹² The Addendum at the end of the paper provides a reconciliation of obverse dies to the die study of ESMs.

¹³ Taylor (2019b): 77-78 for the Group 5 chronology.

gold stater of Group 5 (Type 5.8) bears the same mint controls as tetradrachm Type 5.6, but no laurel wreath is present, other than the one borne in Nike's extended right hand. The wreath symbol would have been redundant in the context of the overall iconography of the stater, with Nike obviously celebrating military victory, the latter symbolized by the laurel wreath held in her extended right hand. The absence of the laurel wreath as a separate symbol from that of the Nike iconography of the stater, suggests that the laurel wreath on the tetradrachms is symbolic of a broader meaning, rather than representing a mint control. It may have been symbolic of Seleukos's early success in wresting control of the provinces of Babylonia, Susiana, and Media from Antigonid control in 312/1 BC.¹⁴

Table 1. Sequence and concordance

	Wreath	Anchor	Other	Mint Controls	SC	Price	ESM
Group 5							
5.1	x			Ϝ	-	3853	-
5.2	x			κ / Ϝ	-	3859	-
5.3	x			ⲗ / Ϝ	-	-	-
5.4	x			PO / Ϝ	-	3855	-
5.5	x			E / Ϝ	-	3854	-
5.6	x			AI / Ϝ	-	3857	-
5.7	erased	x		AI / Ϝ	-	-	-
5.6	x			AI / Ϝ	-	3857	-
5.8 (stater)				AI, Ϝ	-	3856A	-
Group 6							
6.1			Amphora	ΔY	-	3690A	-
6.2			Bee	ΔY	164.5	3689	-
6.3 (stater)			Bee	AY	161	3688	-
6.4			Bee	AY	164.5	3689	-
6.5	x		Shield / Horsehead	BE	164.4b	3865	286
6.6	x		Shield / Horsehead	BE / TI	164.4a	3866	287
6.7 (stater)			Horsehead	EB / TI	160	3864	285
6.8	x		Horsehead	ΔI / I	164.3	3863	284
6.9	x	x	Bull's head	ΔI / I	164.2	3862	283
6.10	x	x		Ϝ / I	-	-	-
6.11	x	x		Ϝ / Ϝ	164.1	3861	-
Group 7							
7.1		x		AE	164.6	3872	290
7.2		x		Α, Σ / AP	-	-	-
7.3		x		Σ / AP	164.8c	3874	293
7.4		x		Α, Σ / ΔP	-	-	-
7.5 (stater)				Α, AP	-	-	-
7.6		x	Kantharos	ⲗ, Σ / ΘE	164.7	-	-
7.7		x		ⲗ, Σ / AP	164.8b	-	-
7.8		erased		ⲗ, Σ / AP	-	-	-
7.9		x		Ϝ, Σ / ΔP	164.8a	3873	292
7.10		x		Ϝ, Σ / AP	164.8a	3873	292
7.11		erased		Σ / AP	-	-	-

Shading denotes die linked types including linked recut reverse dies.

¹⁴ Taylor (2019b): 74 and 80.

Table 2. Susa Groups 5-7. obverse die links.

Group 5 <i>Wreath symbol</i>		Group 6 <i>Various symbols</i>	
5.2 A3	- , $\mathbf{K} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$	6.2 A10	- , \mathbf{AY}
	5.3 A3		- , \mathbf{AY}
5.4 A4	- , $\mathbf{PO} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$	6.4 A11, A12	- , \mathbf{AY}
5.5	- , $\mathbf{E} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$	6.5 A11	- , \mathbf{BE}
5.6 A8	- , $\mathbf{AI} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$	6.6	- , $\mathbf{BE} / \mathbf{TI}$
5.7	- , $\mathbf{AI} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$ <i>anchor recut over wreath on 5.7</i>	6.9 A19	- , $\mathbf{\Delta I} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$
		6.10 A19	- , $\mathbf{\Gamma} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$
		6.11	- , $\mathbf{\Gamma} / \mathbf{\Gamma}$
Group 7 <i>Anchor symbol</i>			
7.2 A21	$\mathbf{\Delta}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$		
7.3 A21	- , $\mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$		
7.4	$\mathbf{\Delta}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{\Delta P}$		
7.6 A23	$\mathbf{\times}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{\Theta E}$	7.9 A24	$\mathbf{\Gamma}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{\Delta P}$
7.7 A23	$\mathbf{\times}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$ <i>anchor erased from reverse die</i>	7.10 A24	$\mathbf{\Gamma}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$ <i>anchor erased from reverse die</i>
7.8	$\mathbf{\times}, \mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$	7.11	- , $\mathbf{\Sigma} / \mathbf{AP}$

The laurel wreath serves to link the striking of Group 5 with Group 6 on which it is accompanied by a number of other symbols. This association of the two groups is reinforced by a hemidrachm bearing the mint controls of Type 5.4 (British Museum G.2500; Price 3856) struck from a reverse die on which the wreath was engraved over a horned horsehead, one of the symbols on Group 6.¹⁵ The chronological association of the two groups is further emphasised by the fact that the $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ primary mint control of Group 5 appears on the last of the Group 6 emission. The latter suggests that Group 5 ceased before the end of the Group 6, thus permitting the mint official designated by the $\mathbf{\Gamma}$ monogram to the oversight of the last of the Group 6 emission (Type 6.11).¹⁶ This interpretation is strengthened further by the identification in the middle of Type 5.6 of a single reverse die recut to display a large vertical inverted anchor in the left field, engraved over the erased laurel wreath

¹⁵ Taylor (2019b): 64.

¹⁶ Taylor (2019b): 74-75. *Seleucid Coins*, based on ESMS, posited that type 6.11 was the first issue of the coinage bearing a laurel wreath plus a secondary symbol (Group 6), whereas the die links established in this study, plus the progression of mint controls and symbolism unequivocally place it as the last issue. This is the most significant of many changes in the sequence established by the current study. Refer Table 1 and the accompanying Addendum for the concordance with prior studies.

(Type 5.7). It appears to have been a trial, or test striking, one that marked the first appearance of Seleukos's anchor seal on coinage.¹⁷ In parallel with this episode, a small horizontal anchor appeared beneath the wreath of the last of the Group 6 issues (Types 6.9 – 6.11). These developments in the application of the anchor symbol preceded the adoption of the anchor symbol as the primary symbol on Group 7.

Group 6 is more diverse than Group 5. Leading Group 6 are four issues (Types 6.1-6.4) reattributed from Babylon to Susa (Price 3688-3690A). These bear an amphora, or bee symbol, while bearing the AY or ΛY mint marks. These two mint marks are interwoven and it is clear from close examination that the engraved Λ was intended as the letter A, potentially an engraving shorthand for such, or an engraving omission of the horizontal crossbar of the letter A.¹⁸ Both AY and ΛY have frequently been misread by previous scholars, resulting in a number of corrections that are noted in the catalogue entries for these types. The reattribution of these issues from Babylon to Susa is confirmed by two die links involving A11 and A12, the former recut in the link, that directly associate the types formerly attributed to Babylon with those of Susa bearing the wreath symbol (Table 2). In this die linked sequence it is clear that the wreath displaced the bee symbol from the coinage, unequivocally placing the types reattributed from Babylon at the head of the Group 6 sequence. Thus, the amphora symbol of Type 6.1 is followed by the bee symbol (Types 6.2-6.4) with the latter obverse die linked by A11 and A12 to the start of the wreath symbol (Types 6.5-6.6). From this point, the laurel wreath was adopted as the primary symbol convention on Group 6 where a progression letter and monogram mint controls, accompanied by secondary symbols, distinguishes it from the Group 5 emission (Table 1). Just as in Group 5, the Group 6 stater issues, Types 6.3 and 6.7, are absent a laurel wreath, other than the one held by Nike, while the bee and horsehead symbols, plus the mint controls found on each, serve to link these staters to the tetradrachms sharing similar symbols and mint controls. Rather than being a separate mint control, the EB mint mark on stater type 6.7 may be the result of an engraving error, a reversal in the placement of the letters on the die that was intended to read BE.

Overlap in the striking of Groups 5 and 6 is evidenced by the laurel wreath symbol engraved over the horned horsehead on a Type 5.4 hemidrachm, plus the presence of the **Π** mint mark, the primary mint control of Group 5, on the last of Group 6 (Type 6.11). With the cessation of Group 5 it appears that the official designated by the **Π** mint mark¹⁹ was charged with responsibility for oversight of the last of Group 6. The parallel development of the anchor symbol late in Group 5 (Type 5.7) and Group 6 (Types 6.9-6.11) strengthens the argument. Episodes of die retouching on Group 5 dies A3 and A8 and Group 6 die A11 suggest that both were struck during a period when the when the mint sought to extend the productive life of existing dies, possibly due to an engraving constraint limiting the supply of new obverse dies. The inferred parallel striking of Groups 5 and 6 in two separate workshops has a precedent in earlier Susa output. Susa Groups 1-3 were similarly struck in parallel in three workshops during the satrapy of Antigenes, attested to by a shared stater die, plus a pattern of shared mint controls.²⁰

Group 7 is defined by a vertically oriented inverted anchor on the reverse left field, plus the appearance of a new suite of mint controls, previously unseen in Groups 5 and 6. The inverted

¹⁷ Taylor (2019b): 71-73.

¹⁸ The same phenomenon is observed in the lettering of the legend, the letter A frequently rendered as L.

¹⁹ Perhaps the *hyparch* Polyarchos identified by *Diodoros* 19.91.3. Refer Taylor (2019b).

²⁰ Taylor (2019a): 57-59 and table 9.

anchor symbol is a progression from the vertical anchor trial engraving on Type 5.7 and the small horizontal anchor symbol that accompanied the laurel wreath on the last of Group 6. On Type 7.6 a small kantharos symbol appears on the inner left field, adjacent to the anchor symbol, accompanied by a Greek monogram mint mark beneath the anchor, the only instance of another symbol in Group 7. The Σ mint control unites all but the first issue (Type 7.1) of this group, accompanied by a well-defined progression of secondary letter and/or monogram mint marks, increasing from one to two in number, which in the last half of the group are also to be found in the left field accompanying the anchor symbol, in addition to those beneath Zeus's throne. Most significantly, two of the Group 7 tetradrachm issues (Types 7.8 and 7.11) were struck from recut reverse dies from which the anchor symbol was erased. This provides a chronological marker that is tied to an identical episode of anchor erasure in the Seleukid mints of Babylonia.²¹ The sole Group 7 stater (Type 7.5) is associated with the tetradrachm series by shared mint controls, although the anchor symbol is absent from the reverse.

Gold staters

The surviving number of gold staters from Groups 5-7 is small. Eight staters, one from each of Groups 5 and 7, plus six from Group 6, are present in the catalogue. In total, four obverse dies are represented, one in each of Groups 5 and 7, two in Group 6. The placement of the staters in the sequence of each group is based on the affinity of the mint controls with counterparts in the tetradrachm sequence. Type 5.8 is known from a solitary specimen in the collection of the American Numismatic Society. Six examples of Type 6.3 were struck from a single obverse die. This type was attributed to Babylon in the period c. 323-317 BC by Price,²² one of four anomalous coin types (Price 3688-90A) that he placed hesitantly at the start of the Babylon sequence following the death of Alexander the Great. It is reattributed to Susa under Seleukos based on the obverse die linkage to the Susa sequence of tetradrachms bearing the same symbol and mint control (Types 6.4-6.6). This is one of several corrections to Price's attribution and typology that are clarified in the catalogue. A second Group 6 stater issue, Type 6.7, bearing the horned horsehead symbol, is known from a single example in the British Museum. It was struck from a different obverse die to that which struck type 6.3. Previously unknown is a Group 7 gold stater (Type 7.5). It bears the Λ and AP mint controls found on some of the Group 7 tetradrachms and has been sequenced accordingly. However, it lacks the anchor symbol, suggesting the possibility that this stater may have been struck at the close of the Group 7 emission when the anchor was erased from two tetradrachm reverse dies (Types 7.8 and 7.11).

Seven plated coins (Cat. Nos. 10-16) imitate stater Type 6.3. These plated coins were struck from two obverse and three reverse dies. The two obverse dies are reverse die linked. The quality of the engraving is poor. The reverse legend is blundered on all three reverse dies. The royal title is rendered as $\text{I}\Lambda\text{S}\text{I}\Lambda\text{E}$, while the name of Alexander appears incomplete and blundered, $\text{A}\Lambda\text{E}\text{E}\Lambda\text{N}\Lambda\text{P}$. The mean weight of the coins is half that of the official issue (Table 3). It is unlikely that they originated from the mint at Susa. Due to the significant departures in epigraphy, iconographic style, and weight from official issues, their acceptance in circulation would have been problematic.

²¹ Taylor (2015) dates the episode of anchor erasure to the period shortly before Seleukos commenced issuing Babylonian coinage in his own name c. 304/3 BC.

²² Price (1991): 454-455 and 469

They foreshadow what was to become the widespread imitation in the broader region of Persis of the later Seleukid silver issues from Susa, in particular the ‘victory coinage’ of Seleukos.²³

Table 3. Stater Metrology.

	N	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Mode (g)	s (g)
Gold staters	9	8.52	8.55	8.55	0.08
Plated counterfeits	7	4.26	4.28	4.28	0.6

Tetradrachms

The Susa Group 5 tetradrachms are documented in detail in a separate paper.²⁴ The tetradrachms of this group were struck from eight obverse dies in a tightly die linked sequence. A large inverted anchor symbol engraved over the laurel wreath in the middle of Type 5.6, plus a laurel wreath engraved over the horned horsehead on a hemidrachm bearing the mint controls of Type 5.4, place Group 5 as a Seleukid coinage, a contemporary of Group 6. The primary mint mark **Π** of Group 5 appears on the last issue of Group 6 strengthening the argument for simultaneous striking of the two groups.

In the catalogue of Group 6 tetradrachms eleven obverse dies are represented. Four of these (A10, A11, A12, and A19) link seven of the nine tetradrachm types in Group 6 (Tables 1 and 2). One obverse die, A11, was paired to 13 reverse dies across three issues (Type 6.4-6.6) to strike about forty percent of the Group 6 catalogue. A11 was a long-lived die, one that underwent significant wear, while being retouched and resurfaced on at least two occasions during the striking of Types 6.5 and 6.6. The wear and recutting was not recognised in prior studies, with the result that the die was identified as four separate dies in the *ESMS* catalogue.²⁵ In its initial state this die struck Type 6.4, formerly attributed to Babylon. Its subsequent use to strike Susa Types 6.5 and 6.6, firmly reattributes Type 6.4 plus the die linked (A10), mint control and symbol linked issues of Types 6.1-6.3 to the mint at Susa. These lead the Group 6 sequence. Type 6.1 is the only example in the catalogue that does not present the royal title ΒΑΣΙΛΕΩΣ in the legend. It depicts Zeus seated with crossed legs, after which the iconography of Zeus reverts to the archaized parallel legs portrayal, other than for Types 6.5, some of 6.6 and 6.8. The crossed legs portrayal first appeared at Susa on a few dies of Susa Group 2 in the period 319/8-317/6 BC, then again on the coinage issued under Aspeias (Susa Group 4), as well as the second half of Group 5, so that its appearance in Group 6 accords with the mint’s variable use of this depiction. The ΛΥ mint control of Type 6.1 links it to Type 6.2 bearing a bee symbol. In turn this is obverse die linked by A10 to Type 6.4 bearing the AY mint control. Die wear on the linking die establishes that the ΛΥ and AY controls were struck in an interwoven manner, indicating that the two controls were interchangeable, the Λ being but an engraving variant of the letter A. In turn, Type 6.4 is doubly die linked by A11 and A12 to the wreath bearing Susa sequence starting with Type 6.5, conclusively establishing the reattribution of Types 6.1-6.4 from Babylon to Susa. The obverse style of Type 6.1 is far more closely aligned to Susa

²³ Marest-Caffey (2016): 12-14.

²⁴ Taylor (2019b).

²⁵ Refer Addendum for the concordance of dies with *ESMS*.

Group 6 than to the Babylon sequence. It has the hallmarks of the earliest Group 6 emission, prior to the establishment of the conventions of legend and symbols that were applied through the balance of Group 6. Collectively, Types 6.1- 6.4 appear to represent a brief period of experimentation before the wreath symbol was established as the most appropriate primary symbol on the coinage.

Group 7 is a small emission of eleven types, struck from only five obverse dies. All but Type 7.1 are obverse die linked. Group 7 is characterized by the presence of a vertically oriented anchor symbol in the left field, on all but the coins struck from the last two reverse dies from which the anchor was erased (Plate 3). The same development occurs on the coinage of Seleukos from his mints at Babylon II and Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) prior to his formal assumption of the royal title in c. 304/3 BC.²⁶ This phenomenon immediately precedes emissions bearing the name of Seleukos in Babylonia. Evidence for this is found in the use of a recut anchor erased reverse die bearing the name of Seleukos (Plate 4, H and I) at Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis). The motivation for the erasure of the anchor symbol was detailed in earlier publications.²⁷ Suffice to say, it confirms that the last of Susa Group 7 must have been struck c. 305/4-304/3 BC. It also indicates that sequence Types 7.6-7.11 were struck in parallel, for the erased anchor is found on the last of the reverse dies paired to each of the two obverse dies (A23-A24) that were used to strike these types. With almost half of the obverse dies in Group 7 used in parallel striking, it is possible that the entirety of the group was minted in a very short period, perhaps a matter of weeks in c. 305/4-304/3 BC.

The episode of anchor erasure from the last two reverse dies of Susa Group 7 precludes the hypothesis that the anchor erasure, previously known only from Babylon II and Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis), may have been the result of Antigonid animosity during the Babylonian War.²⁸ Susa never fell under Antigonid control after Seleukos annexed the province of Susiana in 312/1 BC, so that the erasure of the anchor from dies immediately preceding the emission of coinage in Seleukos's own name cannot have been the result of Antigonid animosity.

STATISTICS

The small sample of gold staters is insufficient to make a confident statistical estimation of the original number of dies that might have been employed to strike the gold coinage. However, at least four stater obverse dies were used, one in each of the Groups 5 and 7 and two in Group 6. The tetradrachm sample of Groups 5-7 consists of 209 coins in which 24 obverse dies are identified.²⁹ The statistical coverage afforded by the sample is high, ranging from 0.95-0.99 across the three groups of tetradrachms (Table 4). As a result, an estimate of the original number of dies used to strike the coinage can be made (Table 4) using the geometrical model of Esty.³⁰ The estimated number of the original dies commissioned for each group falls within a narrow range of uncertainty (95% confidence interval)³¹ of plus or minus two dies (Table 4).

Based on the estimated number of dies employed, Group 6 was the largest of the three

²⁶ Wheatley (2014): 508 and Taylor (2015).

²⁷ Taylor (2015) and Taylor (2019b).

²⁸ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 43.

²⁹ Taylor (2019b) for the Group 5 catalogue of 102 coins struck from 8 obverse dies.

³⁰ Esty (2011).

³¹ Esty (2006): 360, formula 4. This confidence interval defines the range within which a new estimate of the original number of dies based on a new sample of the coinage will fall 95% of the time.

groups; 45 percent larger than Group 5, and more than twice the size of Group 7. The total of the tetradrachm coinage amounted to approximately 540,000 coins,³² equivalent to approximately 355 Attic talents of silver, assuming a weight standard of 17.1 grams per tetradrachm. The gold coinage struck from at least 4 obverse may have been around 40,000 gold staters, the equivalent of 13.2 Attic talents of gold, or 132 Attic talents of silver equivalent.³³ Thus the approximate estimated volume of Groups 5-7 is c. 487 Attic talents of silver equivalent, of which more than 80 percent was associated with Groups 5 and 6. The latter were struck during the period of the Babylonian War (311/0-309/8 BC), most plausibly to help meet Seleukos's requirement for new coinage during this protracted conflict.

Table 4. Tetradrachm statistics.

Group	Sample (<i>n</i>)	Observed dies (<i>d</i>)	Singletons (<i>d</i> ₁)	Estimated original dies (<i>Dest</i>)	Statistical Coverage (<i>Cest</i>)	95% Confidence Interval
5	103	8	1	8.7	0.99	8.0-9.4
6	61	11	3	13.4	0.95	11.3-15.9
7	45	5	1	5.6	0.98	4.9-6.5
5-7	209	24	5	27.1	0.98	25.3-29.1

METROLOGY

The distribution of weights in the sample of gold staters (Table 3) is consistent with adjustment to a weight of slightly less than 8.6 grams per stater. The weight distribution of the tetradrachm sample is summarised in Table 5 and illustrated on Figure 1.

Table 5. Groups 5-7. Tetradrachm weight distribution.

Group	Sample (<i>n</i>)	Mean (g)	Median (g)	Mode (g)	σ (g)
5	102	17.06	17.07	17.03	0.14
6	61	16.85	16.96	17.10	0.47
7	44	17.00	17.07	17.07	0.21
5-7	207	16.98	17.05	17.03	0.30
3σ truncated 5-7	203	17.01	17.05	17.03	0.17

These illustrate that there is no statistical difference in the weight of each of the three groups of tetradrachms, although a higher proportion of worn coins skews the mean and median weight of

³² Assuming an average tetradrachm die productivity of 20,000 coins suggested by Callataj (2011) and a tetradrachm weight standard of 17.12 grams.

³³ Assuming an average stater die productivity of 10,000 coins suggested by Callataj (2011), a 10:1 gold to silver value ratio noted by Le Rider (2007):149 and a mean stater weight of 8.6 grams.

the Group 6 sample to lower values than the equivalent measure in the other groups. As a result, the sample of Group 6 exhibits a standard deviation (σ) that is more than twice that of Groups 5 and 7. To partially account for this, four coins more than three standard deviations (3σ) removed from the mean weight of the total sample (i.e. coins less than 16.1 grams) were discounted in the calculation of the statistics of a truncated distribution of the total sample as presented in Table 5, slightly raising the mean weight of the truncated sample. The weight distribution plotted in half gram increments (Figure 1) shows a strongly developed modal peak across the two weight increments centred on 17.1 grams. The statistics and weight distribution are consistent with *al pezzo* weight adjustment of the coinage to a nominal standard of around 17.1 grams per tetradrachm. This slightly reduced Attic weight standard is consistent with mintage in the closing decade of the 4th century BC. This is similar to that observed in Seleukos’s anchor bearing Alexandrine coinage issued from Babylonia Uncertain Mint 6A in Babylonia.³⁴

Figure 1. Tetradrachm weight distribution.

HOARDS

Documented hoards containing Susa Group 5-7 are few, the earliest dating to the first two decades of the 3rd century BC (Table 6). The Susa coins in these hoards exhibit moderate to high wear, so that the hoard data provides a vague *terminus ante quem* of the early 3rd century for Groups 5-7.

³⁴ Taylor (2015): 54-56, table 4.

Based on the hoard data, the circulation and dispersal of Groups 5-7 was quite restricted relative to that identified in the earlier Susa emissions (Groups 1-3).³⁵ This reflects the differing circumstances of their mintage. Groups 1-3 were struck to pay the mercenaries and troops in the service of Eumenes during his conflict with Antigonos. With Eumenes defeat, his troops were dispersed widely throughout the Macedonian empire, by which means the coinage of these groups was spread far and wide, in very a short period following their mintage. In contrast, Groups 5-7 were struck to pay the troops of Seleukos, based in Susiana and Babylonia, making for a comparatively limited and slow dispersal mechanism.

Table 6. Hoard occurrences documented in the catalogue.

Hoard	Burial			
	BC	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7
Failaka (CH 8.256)	c. 285	-	1 (6.4)	1 (7.1)
Pasargadae II (IGCH 1794)	c. 280	-	1 (6.8)	-
'Seleucus I' (CH 10.265)	c. 281-279	-	2 (6.5, 6.6)	-
Qazvin (IGCH 1796)	c. 275	-	2 (6.8, 6.11)	-
Meydancikkale (CH 8.308)	c. 240-235	1 (5.5)	4 (6.3, 6.4, 6.8)	5 (7.2, 7.6)
Olympia (IGCH 0176)	c. 250-225	1 (5.6)	-	-

CHRONOLOGY

The Susa Group 5 coinage formerly attributed to the satrapy of Aspeisas has been downdated to the era of Seleukos, coincident with the period of the Babylonian War c. 311/0-309/8 BC.³⁶ The coinage of Groups 6-7 was dated the period c. 311-305 BC by Price, with no chronological differentiation between the two groups. Subsequently, *ESMS* followed by *Seleucid Coins* dated some of Group 6 to 311-305 BC, but downdated an early component of Group 6 (types 6.3-6.4), plus Group 7, to the period 298/7-295/4 BC.³⁷ However, the progression of die links, mint controls and symbols, plus the recutting of the wreath over the horsehead symbol on a Group 5 hemidrachm³⁸ indicates that the striking of Group 6 overlapped that of Group 5, and thus falls within the same period, c. 311/0-309/8 BC. During the Babylonian war, as detailed in the Group 5 tetradrachm die study:³⁹

Seleukos's control of Susiana never came under threat. Some of the population of Babylon were even evacuated to Susiana at this time.⁴⁰ With Babylon under Antigonid threat and/or control for much of this period,⁴¹ it is probable that Seleukos relied on his mints at Susa and

³⁵ Taylor (2019a): tables 7 and 8.

³⁶ Taylor (2019b): 78.

³⁷ Houghton and Lorber (2002): 68-69.

³⁸ Price 3856 (BM G.2500), Taylor (2019b): 64

³⁹ Taylor (2019b): 78.

⁴⁰ Grainger (2014): 50.

⁴¹ Grainger (1990): 77-94 and Grainger (2014): 41-53, plus Houghton and Lorber (2002): 1-9.

Ekbatana⁴² to meet his requirements for new coinage. It is into this period, c. 311-308 BC, that the wreath group [Group 5] falls, being among the first issues of Seleukos, preceding his adoption of the anchor symbol on his coinage issued in the name of Alexander. The wreath may have been emblematic of his very early success in 312/1 BC in wresting Babylonia, Susiana, and Media from Antigonid control. Only after firmly vanquishing Antigonid forces in Babylonia in 309/8 BC did the anchor insignia come to identify his authority as the issuer of coinage struck in the name of Alexander.⁴³

Analogous to the anchor bearing Alexanders of Babylonia, Group 7 was most probably struck for the settlement of accounts with troops associated with the return of Seleukos's army in from the eastern anabasis.⁴⁴ This dates the emission to a brief period in c. 305/4-304/3 BC. A firm chronological peg for the end of the emission is provided by the anchor erasure from last reverse dies of Group 7. The same phenomenon is observed at Babylon II and Babylonian Uncertain Mint 6A (Plate 4). Plate 4 (H and I) illustrates two examples of an anchor erased die subsequently recycled and recut to bear the name of Seleukos, among the first coins to bear his name.⁴⁵ This anchor erased reverse die, recut in the name of Seleukos, is obverse die linked (Plate 4, I) to both the anchor bearing and the anchor erased issues in the name of Alexander (Plate 4, F and G). This emphasises the transitional nature of the anchor erasure with respect to the change in the legend from Alexander to Seleukos.⁴⁶ It is most unlikely that the erasure of the Seleukid anchor from dies at three separate mints was the result of a random coincidence. Rather it appears to be a synchronised action, one dated to the period c. 305/4-304/3 BC.⁴⁷ It ended the emission of coinage in the name of Alexander at each of the three mints.

In conclusion, the chronology of Groups 5-7 that flows from the die study requires the updating by up to a decade of a number of issues in the name of Alexander (SC 161, 164.5 – 164.8) relative to that proposed in *Seleucid Coins*. It establishes that no issues in the name of Alexander were struck at Susa following the assumption of the royal title by Seleukos. Subsequent Susa coinage, issued by Seleukos after the battle of Ipsos in 301 BC, exclusively bore the name of Seleukos, initially carried on an emission of innovative iconography.⁴⁸

⁴² Newell (1938): 162-170, Series I, c. 311-303 BC. Newell (1938): 170 '...Series I is better provided with gold staters, and infinitely better provided with fractional denominations than any of the issues which we have here studied for the sister mints of Seleucia, Babylon and Susa.' Boillet (2013): 196 'En reprenant la lecture chronologique des émissions de Séleucos I à Ecbatane telle qu'elle fut établie par Newell dans ses *Eastern Seleucid Mints*, nous apercevons que le début du règne du monarque (311-303 a. C.) fut la période la plus prolifique en frappes monétaires (équivalent tétradrachmes attiques)'... Looking back at the chronology of Seleukos I's emissions in Ekbatana as established by Newell in his *Eastern Seleucid Mints*, we see that the beginning of the monarch's reign (311-303 a. C.) was the most prolific period in monetary strikes (attic tetradrachm equivalents).

⁴³ Taylor (2015).

⁴⁴ Taylor (2015).

⁴⁵ Taylor (2015): Series V, 190-251.

⁴⁶ Immediately prior to the erasure of the anchor symbol from dies at Babylon II and Babylonian Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis) there were some rare minor issues in the name of Seleukos accompanied by the anchor symbol; SC 95, and SC 98 from Babylon II and Taylor (2018) Series V(a) from Uncertain Mint 6A. Based on die links these were trial issues in the transition to coinage in the name of Seleukos, struck immediately prior to the decision to eliminate the anchor symbol from his coinage in the name of Alexander.

⁴⁷ Taylor (2015): 62-75.

⁴⁸ Marest-Caffey (2016): the Susa 'victory coinage.'

Plate 1

AV Staters (1-9) and Counterfeits (11-12)

Tetradrachms

Plate 2

53

54

56

61

66

74

75

76

79

81

84

85

89

90

91

Plate 3

100

103

104

106

107

108

112

116

118

122

Progression of anchor erasure on reverse dies P95 and P100 (enlarged x1.5)

P95

P95 recut1

P95 recut2

P100

P100 recut

Plate 4

Babylonian Mints: examples of tetradrachms from anchor erased reverse dies

Babylon II

A
(anchor)
SC 94.3(c)

B
(erased anchor)
SC -

C
(anchor)
SC 94.4(a)

D
(erased anchor)
SC 94.5

Babylonian Uncertain Mint 6A (Opis)

E
(erased anchor)
SC 67.5(c)

F
(anchor)
SC 67.6

G
(erased anchor)
SC 67.6

In the name of Seleukos

H
(erased anchor)
SC 69.4

I
(erased anchor)
SC 69.7

Plate 4 Coins

- A. ANS 1942.37.1 American Numismatic Society <http://numismatics.org/collection/1942.37.1> accessed February 4, 2019.
- B. LWHT Coll. 160; Spink Numismatic Circular (Mar. 2010), CXVIII, No. 1, GK2870.
- C. LWHT Coll. 161; Pars Coins PCW-G4381.
- D. LWHT Coll. 162; ex-W. K. Raymond Coll.
- E. ANS 1947.98.295 American Numismatic Society <http://numismatics.org/collection/1947.98.295> accessed February 4, 2019.
- F. Peus 401 (3 Nov. 2010), lot 242.
- G. ANS 1944.100.77080 American Numismatic Society <http://numismatics.org/collection/1944.100.77080> accessed February 4, 2019.
- H. LWHT Coll. 196; Heritage 3015 (12 Sep. 2011), lot 25927.
- I. LWHT Coll. 200; ex-Houghton Coll., CSE 938.

ADDENDUM

ESMS included a die study of the tetradrachm coinage classified here as Susa Groups 6 and 7. The concordance of dies identified in this study with those of *ESMS* is presented below.

Table A1. Concordance of dies: Groups 6-7 tetradrachms.

This study	<i>ESMS</i>
A9	-
A10	A11
A11	A5, A7, A8, A9
A12	A8, A10
A13	A6
A14	-
A15	-
A16	A4
A17	A2
A18	A3
A19	A1
A20	A12
A21	A14
A22	-
A23	A15
A24	A13

The die study identified four new obverse dies (A9, A14, A15, and A22), while establishing that ESMS dies A5, A7, A8 and A9 are in fact one die, multiply recut (A11 of this study). ESMS identified two coins (BM 1850,0412.5; ESMS 286 α and ANS 1944.100.72213; ESMS 286 β) as being struck from a single die (ESMS A8) but they are now identified as originating from two different dies, A11 and A12 of this study. Two coins from the Meydancikkale Hoard (*Meydancikkale 2476-7*) that were noted as being from ‘new dies’ in the postscript to ESMS⁴⁹ are from die A23 of this study.

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⁴⁹ Kritt (1997): 139.

⁵⁰ <http://numismatics.org/pella/> accessed 18 November 2019.

⁵¹ <https://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/> accessed 18 November 2019.

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